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Therapeutic targeting in breast cancer for the treatment of lung metastasis: PPP1R1B.

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Metastasis is the major cause of death from cancer and metastasis to the lung in breast cancer is difficult to treat and heterogeneous in nature, complicating its management (1-5). We recently utilized whole transcriptome technologies to define the full complement of differentially expressed kinases and phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer: in the primary tumor, and in metastasis to the CNS (6-8). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (9, 10) to measure total transcription in the lung metastases of humans with breast cancer. We identify here a therapeutic target based on its differential expression and up-regulation upon metastasis to the lung in humans with breast cancer, PPP1R1B, as a candidate therapeutic target for the medical management of lung metastasis.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the lungs to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the lung metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: PPP1R1B.

Results

Figure 1: PPP1R1B is differentially expressed in lung metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

I. Lung metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=6 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=2 lung metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
84152	4.17E-02	1.622	-2.036934	-3.3040737	20400.85	PPP1R1B	3788/22997	98.3

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in lung metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of protein phosphatase 1 regulatory inhibitor subunit 1B, encoded by *PPP1R1B* in metastasis to the lungs in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of PPP1R1B changed more than 98% of the human lung metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,997 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of PPP1R1B messenger RNA in lung metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of PPP1R1B during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

II. Lung metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=6 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=6 lung metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
100155559_TGI_at	4.87E-01	-7.08E-01	-5.0695	-1.44911607	PPP1R1B	23317/52378	55.5

Through measurement of total transcription in the lung metastases of humans with breast cancer as compared to primary tumors of the breast, we validated differential expression of PPP1R1B in metastasis to the lung in breast cancer (**Chart 2**) (10). The expression of PPP1R1B here changed more than 55% of the lung metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 52,378 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of PPP1R1B messenger RNA in lung metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of PPP1R1B during disease progression and dissemination in humans with breast cancer.

1 Thus, differential and increased expression of PPP1R1B defines the lung metastatic transcriptome in
2 human breast cancer.

3 **Discussion**

4 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
5 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
6 trastuzumab). Inhibitors of PPP1R1B, immunoglobulin or small molecule based (once evaluated for
7 toxicity and safety) can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with lung metastasis who have failed
8 previous treatment, with the ultimate goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of lung metastasis in
9 humans with breast cancer who have not yet progressed but are at predicted high risk, or those whose
10 metastasis has not yet become unmanageable due to metastasize size, number or location. A
11 multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis,
12 replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, targeting *CDKN* inactivation and
13 ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting
14 tumor clone resistance (11).
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Methods

We utilized GSE191230 (9) for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the lungs and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE56493 [10] for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods.